

Open Free Energy 2023 - 2024

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Executive Summary

The Open Free Energy project has finished its second year of operation. After a busy year of development and internal validation, we launched our first stable release of the “openfe” toolkit. While there is still much work to be done, this alchemical free energy toolkit is showing promise as a competitive tool for prediction. Many of the highlights of the past year-and-a-half exemplify the benefits of the pre-competitive open source approach.

In 2023, we made a drive to get an early version of our software into partners’ hands. Our partners’ increased usage has delivered us much more direct feedback, and many of the developments and planned improvements detailed later in this report are a result of this valuable feedback. In response to our partners’ feedback, for example, we created a suite of automated analyses that provide insight into the quality of the simulations underlying our free energy calculations, to identify systems that may not be simulated properly.

In April of 2024, we released our first official, stable version of our flagship software package, **openfe v1.0**. With this release, we commit to maintain existing functionality and behavior for the planned future. This stable release marks our transition from a fledgling software development project to a multi-faceted scientific software

endeavor, with a growing need to balance competing priorities of maintenance and stability, feature development, scientific validity, and performance.

Early benchmarking results show promising accuracy. One of our partners (Bayer) compared results from our RBFE protocol against industry standard proprietary methods on a small set of 12 transformations and found comparable performance..

RBFE calculations performed at Bayer using the OpenFE workflow (with the OpenFF “Sage” and AMBER99SB-ILDN) to two versions of the OPLS force field in FEP+.

Along the way, we have encountered several issues, which we have often fixed in collaboration with the developers of neighboring software packages. This results in improvements both internally for the immediate benefit of the project, but also more broadly fixed upstream to benefit the entirety of open source computational chemistry. As one example, we identified a bug in AmberTools that can lead to large variability in the partial charges assigned to a given molecule, which was causing extremely large variance in our predicted ddG for some systems.

Finally, this first version of the toolkit is only the start. Our roadmap for 2024 and beyond will broaden the available methods and their domain of applicability. In addition to the work of the project developers, we are expecting many contributions to the Open Free Energy ecosystem from external developers.

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Introduction

This report summarizes the progress made on activities funded by the Open Free Energy Fund between January 2023 and July 2024. This year-and-a-half reporting period allows us to shift onto a mid-year reporting schedule that aligns more closely with the schedule of our membership renewals.

Organization and personnel

The Open Free Energy Fund is a project fund hosted by the Open Molecular Software Foundation (OMSF), a 501(c)(3) nonprofit based in Davis, California, USA. Open Free Energy (OpenFE) refers to the complete set of activities supported by this fund, which include software development, maintenance, benchmarking, and some supporting research. OpenFE (sometimes stylized as **openfe**) also refers to the flagship software package produced by this project as its primary output. OMSF acts as a fiscal sponsor and provides administrative services, including accounting services and employing the software development team. OMSF also hosts other projects that are closely tied to Open Free Energy, including Open Force Field and ASAP, and serves as a hub for the development of an open source software ecosystem in the molecular sciences.

The development team has consisted of six software developers, a project manager, and a technical writer:

- Richard J. Gowers, Project Director
- David W.H. Swenson, Infrastructure Lead
- Irfan Alibay, Science Lead
- James Baggs Eastwood (50% FTE), Project Manager
 - Shared with Open Force Field Initiative
- Hannah Baumann, Scientific Software and Methods Developer
- Benjamin Ries (50% FTE), Scientific Software and Methods Developer
 - Benefit in kind contribution from Boehringer Ingelheim
- Mike M. Henry (50% FTE), Software Scientist
 - Contribution from Chodera lab
- Josh Mitchell, Scientific Communicator (25% FTE)
 - Subcontracted from Open Force Field Initiative, Q3 2023

The development team has experienced turnover in key positions during the first half of 2024. In January, David Swenson accepted a position leading OMSF's new ecosystem infrastructure team. In May, Richard Gowers resigned. These two vacancies have left the team with a notable deficit in software engineering expertise, but also present a rare opportunity to rethink the team structure and rebalance our capabilities. A major priority for Q3 2024 is to hire two new team members: a senior Research Software Engineer to take ownership of our infrastructure, and a Software Scientist to provide application support and contribute to scientific benchmarking and method development.

Technical Advisory Committee

The Technical Advisory Committee (TAC) is a group of recognised experts who offer technical guidance and feedback on potential and ongoing efforts undertaken by the development team. Participation on the committee is on a voluntary basis and members are invited with approval of the board to avoid potential conflicts of interest.

Table 1: List of Open Free Energy Technical Advisory Committee members

2024 Technical Advisory Committee Membership	
Name	Institution
Oliver Beckstein	Arizona State University
Phil Biggin	University of Oxford
Stefan Boresch	Universität Wien
John Chodera	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center
Zoe Cournia	Academy of Athens
Peter Eastman	Stanford University
Emilio Gallicchio	Brooklyn College CUNY
Antonia Mey	University of Edinburgh
Julien Michel	University of Edinburgh
David Mobley	University of California at Irvine
Bharath Ramsundar	Deep Forest Sciences
Michael Shirts	University of Colorado at Boulder
Jonah Vilseck	Indiana University School of Medicine

Recap of previous progress

In Year 1 of our project, our main focus was on building an initial workflow for relative binding free energy (RBF) calculations. One of our major undertakings was the development of “gufe” (Grand Unified Free Energy), a modular and extensible Python library. This library was designed to enhance interoperability among different free energy projects and to promote future growth, by both our developer team and external contributors. In the gufe library, we incorporated two key components. Firstly, we developed data models that describe chemical systems and alchemical transformations. Secondly, we integrated abstract application

programming interfaces (APIs) that define how different components should interact to ensure robust interoperability. These APIs include tools for atom mapping and network planning as well as features to conveniently serialize and store objects. We made use of atom mapping and scoring tools from the LOMAP and perses packages, and implemented two network planners, allowing users to generate radial networks (star maps) and minimal spanning graphs.

Our first year efforts focused on the development of an OpenMM-based protocol to carry out RBFЕ calculations, based on the Perses framework developed by the Chodera lab. This protocol enables the calculation of pairwise free energies for ligand transformations in gas phase, solvent, and protein complexes. The workflow takes as inputs two ChemicalStates that define the end states of the alchemical transformation (created, for example, from a set of pre-docked ligands and a fully modeled protein structure), an atom mapping, and simulation settings. Sampling of λ states can either be achieved through a standard independent windows approach, or can be enhanced using Hamiltonian Replica Exchange or Self-Adjusted Mixture Sampling. After execution, the workflow generates an MBAR-derived free energy estimate.

Throughout Year 1, we carried out comprehensive benchmarking and validation exercises to assess the performance and accuracy of our protocols, using a small validation set of hydration free energies of benzene derivatives, as well as a larger protein-ligand benchmark set. The results showed that our method reasonably reproduced experimental values, suggesting that the RBFЕ Protocol was working as intended.

Usability and Maintenance of Existing Tools

OpenFE entered Year 2 of our project (calendar year 2023) owning several libraries, protocols, and other tools resulting from the efforts of Year 1. This section describes the team's efforts to maintain and improve these products and support our users.

Partner Onboarding and Usage Drive

During this reporting period, OpenFE reached an important inflection point, where emphasis shifted from being entirely focused on adding functionality to the software platform, toward a new focus on getting OpenFE into the hands of real users. In anticipation of this, we improved our documentation and developed a tutorial on doing an RBFЕ, each discussed below.

Now that some of our partners are trying OpenFE, we have focused on obtaining their feedback and using that feedback to improve the software. As an example, we significantly improved our installation experience after our earliest users found our original instruction tedious and difficult.

Our improved installation process is commonly mentioned as a very positive experience by our users. Feedback from our early-adopter partners also encouraged us to prioritize more detailed analysis functionality, and to make some performance improvements in the network planning step.

We continue to focus on getting our partners to try OpenFE in their own environments, and on their own benchmark datasets. From their experiences, we will identify what adjustments we need to make to OpenFE so that it fits smoothly into many different workflows.

Documentation

As another aspect of our increased emphasis on users, we have made major improvements to our documentation during this reporting period. This is an ongoing effort, which has included significant improvements to both content and presentation of the OpenFE documentation, available at <https://docs.openfree.energy/>.

The documentation has been updated to follow the [Diátaxis](#) approach for documentation. The API reference was overhauled to ensure that it is more complete, and a “cookbook” of how-to guides has been added. This cookbook can be navigated by a flowchart, shown in Fig. 1, which illustrates the overall workflow of setting up a network of RBEF calculations, where each step links to a small guide. Some sections, such as the User Guide/Explanation, are still in development.

OpenFE Documentation

Installation Tutorials User Guide Cookbook Reference

Search [Ctrl] + [K]

Cookbook

This section describes common tasks involving the OpenFE Python API.

The [OpenFE CLI](#) provides a simple way to perform the most common procedures for free energy calculations, but does not provide much flexibility for fine-tuning your approach or combining OpenFE with other tools. The [Python API](#) allows that flexibility, but using it is more complex. This cookbook breaks down common steps that would be implemented in Python to help navigate that complexity.

Note

This section is a work-in-progress.

The Basic Workflow

The typical way to use the Python API is to load a number of molecules you want to calculate free energies of, construct a [LigandNetwork](#) connecting them in an efficient way, and then combine that with information for how each ligand should be simulated to construct an [AlchemicalNetwork](#), which specifies the entire simulation campaign. This provides a lot of flexibility in how molecules are specified, mapped, connected, and simulated, without exposing a great deal of complexity. OpenFE recommends this workflow for most users.

Setup

Chemical component definition
SDF, PDB, RDKit, OpenFF Molecule, solvent spec, etc.

Loading proteins, Defining solvents
↓
SolventComponent and ProteinComponent
Other chemical components needed to simulate the ligand.

Loading small molecules
↓
SmallMoleculeComponent
The ligands that will be mutated.

OrionFEP+
Atom mappings from another tool.

dict or list
Hand-write an atom mapping.

Network Loaders (two instances)

LigandNetwork
A network of ligand transformations.

Protocol
Simulation procedure for an alchemical mutation.

AlchemicalNetwork
A complete simulation campaign.

Run

Dumping a Transformation to JSON

openfe quickrun
OpenFE recommends using the `openfe quickrun` CLI command to execute a transformation.

Gather

openfe gather
OpenFE recommends using the `openfe gather` CLI command to collect the results of a transformation.

Develop and launch modern apps with MongoDB Atlas, a resilient data platform.
Ad by EthicalAds

Figure 1: Cookbook section of OpenFE documentation

Tutorial

In preparation for the May 2023 OMSF meeting, we developed an introductory tutorial for users of OpenFE. This tutorial shows how to perform relative binding free energy calculations for 11 ligands that bind to TYK2. The tutorial provides easy commands with which one can download the tutorial materials, and then takes the

user through the steps in creating a network of simulations, shows how one would run the simulations, and then has the user download pre-calculated results to see how to gather results from the multiple independent simulations. It includes a Jupyter notebook that does the same setup as the command line, to illustrate how users could customise various parts of the setup.

In addition to the RBFEE tutorial, we have a [“Showcase” tutorial](#), which acts as a whistle-stop tour through much of the functionality of OpenFE. This Showcase was updated for the May 2024 OMSF meeting to highlight the features of v1.0.

Partner Benchmark Results

As previously mentioned, a major focus of our work this year has been to get the OpenFE tooling into the hands of users. This is a crucial step in evaluating the ever-growing OpenFE ecosystem and ensuring that non-experienced users can achieve expected free energy endpoints on user-prepared systems. As part of these efforts, the OpenFE team has been working with members of the board and helping them trial the OpenFE relative binding free energy tooling on their internal datasets. This has provided us with valuable feedback to refine our tooling and direct future development efforts. Notably, user feedback has led to the continued development of the OpenFE CLI (see below), and the addition of automated post-simulation analysis (see Method Development). Smaller improvements; such as adding the ability to load transformation networks from Schrodinger FEP+ and OpenEye inputs, have also been spurred by these benchmarks.

Due to confidentiality concerns, only one of our board partners, Bayer, was able to share their results for this report (led by Joseph Bluck). The results of their work, calculating relative binding free energies on a small subset of 12 transformations (11 ligands), using both OpenFE (v0.6.1) and Schrodinger’s FEP+ is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. RBFEE calculations performed at Bayer using the OpenFE workflow (with the OpenFF “Sage” and AMBER99SB-ILDN) to two versions of the OPLS force field in FEP+.

Whilst OpenFE has only been tested on a limited number of systems, results seem promising, with the tooling for the most part offering results on par with, or even sometimes outperforming, commercial offerings. It is worth noting that the selected systems were specifically limited to those that OpenFE could support at the time

of calculation, e.g. no systems involving charge changes, membrane-proteins, or scaffold hopping were evaluated. Feedback generally praised the ease of setup and use of the OpenFE tooling. Conversely, issues surrounding setup and simulation performance (roughly two times slower than FEP+), generated file sizes, and difficulties with simulation analysis were raised. Efforts, such as switching away from the slow LOMAP mapper to Kartograf and the introduction of automated post-simulation analysis, are currently under way to mitigate these issues.

CLI Advancements

As part of our drive toward better usability, we have extended the OpenFE CLI to simplify some common tasks. As of the last report, we had provided a CLI tool to run a single leg of a simulation, a tool we called **quickrun**. However, the user was still responsible for creating a JSON file for each leg, and for assembling the results that came out of that into a usable table. During this period, we developed the CLI tools **plan-rbfe-network** and **plan-rhfe-network** to create the JSON files suitable as input to **quickrun**, and we developed the CLI tool **gather** to assemble the results from that into a table of results. By default, we provide estimates of absolute free energies obtained from maximum likelihood analysis, but users can also specifically request the relative free energy differences or the raw values from each leg.

We have also added the CLI subcommand **view-ligand-network** to visualize the alchemical transformations between ligands, as well as convenience commands **fetch** to download various datasets and **test** to run the OpenFE test suite. Additionally, settings can now be configured from the CLI by passing a **.yaml** file specifying the desired settings.

Ecosystem Maintenance

As well as developing new functionality and features into our software we are also committed to ensuring that all existing functionality remains stable. Our software is built on a tall stack of other software, and therefore issues that are encountered can sometimes be traced back to elsewhere in this stack. Our strategy for handling these cases is to first fix the issue locally within our software, ensuring a quick fix, and secondly to work with the upstream software to fix the problem at source.

Working in this way ensures that these issues are fixed for everyone working with biomolecular simulation and builds relationships with other development teams, both of which are key to the long term strategy of the Open Free Energy project. Examples of this approach include minor changes such as [ensuring that ACE caps in PDB structures are correctly read by rdkit](#), or that [structural waters in protein complexes aren't replaced by ions during solvation in OpenMM](#).

Ambertools partial charge bug

Not all issues are as easily resolved, and some require a mixture of software engineering and scientific knowledge to fix. An ongoing issue we have found is that partial charge assignment using Antechamber / AM1-BCC can lead to significant issues in the reproducibility of calculated alchemical free energies.

Specifically we found i) inconsistencies in the chosen conformer for partial charge assignment and ii) unstable partial charge assignment for a predetermined conformer.

Figure 3: Overview of partial charge assignment within the OpenFF toolkit.

Inconsistencies in chosen conformer partial charges. The OpenFE Protocols use the OpenFF toolkit for charge assignment. By default the OpenFF toolkit's behavior, when not using the OpenEye backend, for AM1BCC charge assignment is to first generate a new conformer via RDKit with a set random seed and then calculate charges using Antechamber (Figure 1). Unfortunately, it was found that this can lead to significantly different conformers being selected across different machines. In turn, these conformers may end up with differing partial charges, leading to discontinuities in thermodynamic cycles, as partial charges are re-calculated for solvent and complex legs of every ligand transformation. This can be seen in Figure 2 where we compare binding free energy outcomes for the Hif2A benchmark set. Here we see that default charge assignment (Figure 2A) can lead to exceedingly large uncertainties (standard deviation between 3 repeats) which are not seen when enforcing that input conformer is used for partial charge assignment (Figure 2B). Specifically looking at the gas phase transformations of ligand 336 to ligand 338 in the HIF2A set, we find that two different partial charge populations can be occupied. These lead to estimates of the free energies which differ by 9 kcal/mol (Figure 3).

Figure 4: Correlation between calculated and experimental DDG values for HIF2a. Partial charges were assigned using either a random conformer (A, default charge assignment) or using the input conformer (B). The default charge assignment led to large uncertainties that were not seen when using the input conformers.

Figure 5 (A) Partial charge difference between the two sets of partial charges of HIF2a ligand 338. For one atom the difference between the two sets is greater than 0.07. (B) Histogram of DDG values of transforming HIF2a ligand 336 to ligand 338 in vacuum in 100 repeats. DDG values differ by ~ 9 kcal/mol, depending on the assigned partial charges of ligand 338.

Unstable partial charge assignment for a predetermined conformer. Despite enforcing a specific conformer for partial charge generation, we found that in some cases there can be a large variability in assigned partial charges. To demonstrate this, we compare benchmarks of P38 and SHP2 with either partial charges which have been recalculated using the input conformer for each repeat of each leg of the thermodynamic cycle (Figure 4A), or a single pre-supplied set of partial charges for all calculations involving a given ligand (Figure 4B). Much larger uncertainties are observed in the former case. Isolating a specific ligand from SHP2 (E3), we find that antechamber's SQM engine can optimize a single geometry to two different conformations, leading to different partial charges being assigned (Figure 5).

Figure 6: Correlation between calculated and experimental DDG values for P38 (left plots) and SHP2 (right plots). Partial charges were assigned using the input conformer and recalculated for each repeat of each leg of the thermodynamic cycle (A) or a single pre-supplied set of partial charges for all calculations involving a given ligand was used (B). Larger uncertainties were obtained when regenerating partial charges (A).

Figure 7: Conformation of two SQM optimized geometries of SHP2 ligand E3. Even though the same input conformation was used, the optimization converged to different geometries resulting in differences in atomic partial charges.

This issue is reproducible even when using a single compute machine for all partial charge calculations. It was found that this issue was, at least partially, caused by the choice of SQM options employed by Antechamber which led to the automated choice of diagonalization routines based on machine performance heuristics. Due to slight differences in floating point handling and convergence evaluations between each routine, we find that their choice directly influences the minimized geometry. Early results demonstrate that enforcing a diagonalization routine and tightening the density matrix convergence criteria may resolve these issues.

Towards a solution. The OpenFE team is currently engaged in finding a solution to this issue. Ongoing work is concentrating on; i) evaluating more reproducible approaches to conformer selection for partial charge generation such as ELF¹, ii) testing the influence of passing more detailed SQM parameters on free energy benchmarks across homogeneous compute systems.

Continuous Delivery and QA

As the OpenFE software product has matured, we have adapted our testing strategy to reflect the stability desired by our partners. We have two different testing strategies which allow us to continue to rapidly iterate on features while also releasing a stable product. New features and bug fixes are tested with hundreds of isolated unit tests to check that each component functions as expected. We also run these tests on a regular schedule so we can catch bugs introduced by our software dependencies. This allows us to be proactive and catch bugs before they affect users.

Our second testing strategy is to validate our entire software pipeline (end-to-end) from the beginning with network setup and planning, all the way to the end with free energy analysis of an alchemical network. We currently run the TYK2 benchmark, but as we add new protocols, we are also expanding the systems we test. This kind of testing requires HPC scale resources and is manually performed before we release a new software version. By manually testing the pipeline (orchestration, network planning, alchemical simulations, free energy analysis) in the same way that our users use our software, we can ensure that everything works together instead of only testing components individually in an isolated environment.

Method Development Progress

Here we highlight the work done by the OpenFE team to continue to develop and evaluate new and existing tooling for free energy calculations. Work has primarily focused on making the core OpenFE offering, a relative free energy (RFE) protocol using OpenMM, accessible and ready for evaluation by interested parties.

Continual Benchmarking

Figure 8: Correlation between calculated and experimental DDG values for the 9 test systems (TYK2, MCL1, Hif2A, P38, CDK2, PDE2, PFKFB3, PTP1B, SHP2).

Figure 9: Correlation between calculated and experimental ΔG values for the 9 test systems (TYK2, MCL1, Hif2A, P38, CDK2, PDE2, PFKFB3, PTP1B, SHP2). Note centralized around zero.

Introduction In order to evaluate the status of the OpenFE relative binding free energy tooling, we have undertaken the task of continually working towards new and improved relative binding free energy benchmarks. Here we demonstrate our results on a subset of systems from the current status (see “Key Collaborations” for more details) of the [Protein-Ligand benchmark set](#).

Methods Here we present the results of benchmarks for 211 ligands across 9 systems; TYK2, MCL1, Hif2A, P38, CDK2, PDE2, PFKFB3, PTP1B, and SHP2. Due to continual improvements in the protein-ligand benchmark, these structures are different from those used in the previous year. To differentiate between the two, we identify the benchmarks presented here as the **2023 benchmark set**, and those employed in the year 1 report as the **2022 benchmark set**. Some systems from the 2022 benchmark set have not been included here (notably Thrombin and TNSK2) due to the introduction of new ligands with net charge changes.

Minimum spanning tree networks for the 2023 benchmark set were generated with Kartograf mappings without core-core element changes (see RBF E improvements for more details). For each transformation, three individual repeats were calculated, each using Hamiltonian replica exchange over 11 equidistant lambda windows, with 1 ns of equilibration and 5 ns of production time per window. Exchanges were attempted every picosecond. Simulation results are reported as the average estimate of the three replicate simulations and error bars are set as the standard deviation between individual estimates.

All simulations were calculated under NPT conditions with a target temperature and pressure of 298 K and 1 atmosphere respectively. Temperature and pressure control was achieved using Langevin dynamics (using a VRORV splitting)², and a MonteCarlo barostat³. Simulated systems were parameterized using a combination of AMBER ff14SB⁴, OpenFF 2.0⁵, and tip3p⁶ for protein, small molecule and water components respectively. Nonbonded interactions were handled using a 1 nm short range cutoff and PME^{7,8} for long range electrostatics. In all cases, a HMR scheme was employed, allowing for a 4 fs integration step.

Results and discussion In Figures 8 and 9 we report the calculated DDG and MLE derived DG values for each system compared to experimental values. Overall we find that our results agree well with experiment, with the majority of systems demonstrating sub 1.5 kcal/mol RMSE and MUE values. The quality of correlation metrics vary significantly between systems; we find reasonable Pearson correlations for TYK2, MCL1, CDK2, and PFKFB3. By comparison, much worse correlation metrics are seen for other systems including a seemingly negative correlation for PDE2. This variation is expected, being partly affected by both a combination of sampling difficulty, experimental quality, and limited dynamic range in affinities.

Analysis of inter-replica standard deviations demonstrates that simulations generally converge well, with the majority of errors falling below 0.5 kcal/mol (Figure 10A). However, we do see some cases of very large error bars, particularly for P38 and PDE2 where the standard deviation exceeds 3 kcal/mol for some edges. For some of these cases, this appears to be caused by poor input structures. For example in P38 we find a key ring in the shared scaffold with different puckers (Figure 10B). Current analyses indicate that slow interconversions in ring

conformations are leading to large fluctuations in free energies. PDE2 is still under investigation, no causes for the large error bars have been found yet.

(A)

(B)

Figure 10: (A) Histogram of standard deviations across all systems. Standard deviations were calculated from three independent repeats. The majority of errors fall below 0.5 kcal/mol. (B) Input conformation of ligands 3fn and 2gg in the P38 system. Different starting conformation of ring systems in the P38 systems can lead to sampling problems and larger errors (standard deviation in transformation from ligand 3fn to ligand 2gg sdv=3.2 kcal/mol).

Despite the above we see that, for the shared subset of systems (MCL1, Hif2A, TYK2, and P38), our results are comparable to the 2022 benchmark set results presented in our first year report. This indicates that: a) no significant regressions in the performance of the relative binding free energy tooling is seen, b) continual improvements to the protein-ligand benchmark have not significantly affected expected outcomes. To verify the lack of regression in the tooling, benchmarks of the four most well behaved 2022 benchmark systems were carried out (not shown). No statistically significant differences to previously reported results were observed.

Conclusion and Future work The benchmark results presented here demonstrate that the OpenFE relative binding free energy tooling is working as expected. Some issues with the current benchmark inputs have been identified and will be addressed in future remediations of the protein-ligand benchmark set. In the next few months we hope to extend our benchmark sets to explore; i) the effect of different network types (LOMAP, HiMAP, and radial), and ii) the impact of different mappers (Kartograf and LOMAP), on the estimated free energies.

RFE calculations feature Improvements

This section outlines some of the features which have been added to the OpenFE Hybrid Topology Relative Free Energy Protocol over the last year. As the key offering of the OpenFE project, it is our aim to continue to invest time towards improving this Protocol over the coming years.

Charge Changing Transformations

Due to the introduction of finite size effects^{9,10}, directly calculating transformations between ligands with net charge transformations in PME cannot be achieved without introducing error in the free energy estimates. To avoid this, various approaches have been proposed to either ensure a consistent neutral system across the various states of an alchemical transformation¹⁰⁻¹⁴, or by introducing post-simulation analytical corrections^{9,15}. To enable net charge changes in our relative binding free energy protocol, we have implemented an explicit charge correction based on the Perses implementation by Ivy Zhang et al.^{16,17}. Here a randomly picked water molecule, beyond a user-supplied distance from the system solutes (default 0.8 nm), is simultaneously transformed to an ion during a charged alchemical transformation (Figure 11). This ensures that the end states remain neutral. We note two key caveats to this approach. Firstly only the addition of either a single sodium or chloride ion are supported, limiting net charge transformations to an absolute value of 1. Secondly, charge changing transformations require more sampling: we found a need to perform transformations using 22 lambda windows, each run for a production length of 20 ns, in order to obtain good convergence in our benchmarking systems. This is significantly longer than our simulation defaults of 11 windows with 5 ns of production simulation.

Figure 11: depiction of the co-transformation of an ion alongside the main alchemical transformation.

The performance of this explicit charge correction method was evaluated on a selection of test systems. We first tested the implementation on a CDK2 system¹⁸ with one charged ligand and 10 neutral ligands (Figure 12). For a radial network of charge changing transformations, using the charged ligand as the central ligand, we obtained good convergence as determined by a low standard deviation across three repeats (Figure 12A). The results are also closer to experiment, by approximately 0.6 kcal/mol, than those calculated using no explicit charge correction (Figure 12B). As an additional assessment of convergence, redundant edges were added to the radial network, and a cycle closure error was calculated (Figures 12C and 12D). Cycle closure errors were observed to not exceed 0.5 kcal/mol for all 45 ligand cycles in this network, suggesting converged free energy estimates.

Figure 12: Charge changing transformations in the CDK2 system. (A, B, C) Correlation between calculated and experimental DDG(left) and DG (right) for a radial (A, B) and a redundant network (C) of CDK2 ligands. DDG values present the mean and standard deviation from three independent repeats. (A) A negatively charged ligand was used as the central ligand in the radial map, while all other ligands were neutral such that all transformations involved charge changes. (B) Results from the same radial network as in (A), but no explicit charge correction was applied. (D) Histogram of cycle closure values (summation of DDG in a ligand cycle) for all cycles in the redundant network (C).

We then tested the explicit charge correction protocol on additional systems from the Schrodinger FEP+ net charge benchmark set.^{10,19} As shown in Figure 13, we obtained comparable results to those calculated via FEP+ in the aforementioned study. We note that the CDK2 system has a poorer performance with OpenFE, the exact cause of this is currently unclear. The FEP+ results use both a different force field and sampling methodology¹⁹, which could have affected a direct comparison of the results.

Figure 13: Comparison of the performance of OpenFE and FEP+ on charge changing transformations in four test systems (EPHX2, TYK2, CDK2, PTP1B). Correlation between calculated and experimental DDG is shown for each method.

For a subset of these systems, we compared the influence of using explicit charge correction using the alchemical water against simulations without charge corrections (Figure 14). Overall, we found that the DDG values obtained using explicit charge correction (Figure 13) correlated better with experimental values than those without (Figure 14). This demonstrates that the correction is able to overcome some of the artifacts introduced when simulating systems with net charges.

Figure 14: Comparison between the explicit charge correction protocol and a protocol that does not correct for the change in net charge.

To ensure the validity of our implementation, we compared the Perses implementation of the alchemical water charge correction against the OpenFE implementation. For three transformations in the CDK2 system (Figure 15) both implementations gave very similar results.

Figure 15: Comparison of the performance of OpenFE and Perses on three transformations in the CDK2 system. Shown is the correlation between calculated and experimental DDG (first two plots) and the correlation between calculated DDG using OpenFE and Perses (third plot). Results from the OpenFE and Perses protocols are very similar for these three transformations.

Finally, we tested the alchemical water protocol on a larger TYK2 dataset. Calculations were performed for two radial maps, both having a charged ligand (one positive, one negatively charged) as a central ligand while the rest of the ligands were neutral. This is designed such that all transformations in the alchemical network involve changes in the net charge of the system (Figure 16). Overall results look encouraging, offering a good comparison with experimental values in MLE derived DGs. However, for one of the networks (Figure 16A) we observe a systematic shift in the DDG values of roughly 1 kcal/mol compared to experiment which will require further investigation.

(A) TYK2 radial map

- Central ligand: -1
- All other ligands: 0

(B) TYK2 radial map

- Central ligand: +1
- All other ligands: 0

Figure 16: Correlation between calculated and experimental DDG (upper plots) and DG (lower plots) for two radial maps for the TYK2 system. (A) A negatively charged ligand is used as the central ligand in the radial map while the other 16 ligands are neutral. (B) A positively charged ligand is used as the central ligand while the other 16 ligands are neutral.

In conclusion, we have implemented an explicit charge correction for relative binding free energies in openfe using alchemical waters. As expected, this approach outperforms using no correction and for the most part seems to match results obtained using alternative methods, including FEP+ and Perses. Further work will concentrate on evaluating the performance of this method on larger benchmark sets and exploring the cause of observed systematic errors.

Support for core atom element changes

Figure 17: a) Example of a core-core element change mapping where the (blue) mapped carbon and oxygens are interpolated, b-c) calculated $\Delta\Delta G$ for PFKFB3 LOMAP networks with and without element change transformations respectively, d) distribution of sampling errors (standard deviation between replicate simulations) for simulations with and without element changes.

A key limitation of the RFE protocol was an inability to handle particles changing elements in the core region, i.e. atoms which are directly mapped between end states and are directly interpolated rather than being turned into dummy atoms (Figure 17A). Instead, element changes could only be handled by making the necessary atoms turn into dummy atoms. Whilst this did not have any issues in most cases, it could lead to large perturbations, particularly when the element change was part of a ring atom, leading to the entire ring being excluded from the core atom region.

To address this, the functionality for handling element changes was added back to the RFE protocol. Similar to the approach used in Perses, no mass scaling is employed here. Instead the core atom is given the average mass of the atoms in each endstate. We take this approach based on the idea that particle masses do not affect thermodynamic averages, and should allow correct free energies to be recovered.^{20,21} To evaluate this, we carried out simulation of the PFKFB3 system for LOMAP networks with and without element changes. As demonstrated in Figure 17B-C, no significant differences in calculated free energies were observed, demonstrating that the approach employed does not introduce any additional errors. We do note slightly higher inter-replicate standard deviations when using element changes, which may indicate that core atom element changes are harder to converge (Figure 17D). Further investigations will look to evaluate the influence of such perturbations on a wider range of benchmark datasets.

Support for spectator molecule handling

Explicit support for non-alchemical spectator small molecules (e.g. co-factors) has been added to the openfe Protocols. This is handled by passing an additional spectator `SmallMoleculeComponent` to each state of the transformation. Parameterization is handled by the same small molecule force field used for the transforming ligand, namely `OpenFF` or `GAFF`. Applications of this cofactor handling can be seen in the PFKFB3 simulations shown in the sections above (benchmarking and core-core element changes). We note the following limitations; i) metal containing cofactors cannot be parameterized, and ii) a separate force field from the transforming ligand cannot be applied. Ongoing work will aim to alleviate some of these issues by allowing for arbitrary mixing of compatible force fields.

Support for non-alchemical waters with virtual sites

Limitations in the generation of hybrid topologies prevented the use of non-three site waters in relative free energy calculations. As a result of requests by key partners, support has been added for non-alchemical waters with virtual sites. Specifically, hybrid topologies can now be constructed for molecules containing `OpenMM ThreeParticleAverageSite` particles. Validation tests on a small set of relative solvation free energies demonstrates this to work as expected for `TIP4P-ew` (Figure 18). Further validation by our collaborators is expected in the coming year.

Figure 18: Comparison of calculated $\Delta\Delta G$ for the benzene relative hydration set using TIP3P (3-site) and TIP4P-Ew (4-site) water.

Post Simulation Analysis

To aid in recognising untrustworthy calculations and subsequent debugging, a variety of post simulation analysis has been added to the openfe RFE Protocol, which can be categorized as either energetics analysis or structural analysis.

The energetics analysis is implemented using a combination of OpenMMTools²² and PyMBAR²³, and includes the following analyses:

- [Forward and reverse convergence](#)
 - Shown below on the left. In this example we can see that the simulation has not converged to a satisfactory value by the end of the calculation.
- MBAR overlap matrix and replica exchange matrix
 - Shown below on the right for a different calculation, this shows that there is enough mixing between lambda states.
- Replica state time series

Figure 19: Representative plots for the Forward and Reverse convergence and MBAR overlap matrix plots. These are from different calculations.

The structural analysis is built upon the MDAnalysis package and is designed to detect common failure cases where either large conformational changes in the protein have occurred or the ligand has changed pose or drifted from the binding site. Types of analyses provided include::

- Protein 2D RMSD plots, highlighting any structural changes in the protein over the course of the simulation
- Ligand RMSD and COM drift, highlighting if the ligand has significantly changed pose or position in each replica

Figure 20: Showing the 2D Protein RMSD and Ligand COM drift plots.

Molecular Dynamics

In some cases, such as pre-equilibrating a protein-ligand system in preparation for free energy calculations or gaining insight into the dynamics of the system, a user may desire to run a “plain” MD simulation with no alchemical transformations, but otherwise configured identically to the corresponding alchemical simulation. We have implemented an MD protocol to allow OpenFE to be run in this way, along with a [tutorial on running a molecular dynamics simulation in OpenFE](#).

Absolute Free Energies

To extend the capabilities of the openfe toolkit and enable future methodologies such as Separated Topologies^{24,25}, the OpenFE team has been working on adding support for absolute free energy calculations. This is taking the form of a partial decoupling workflow (Figure 21) based on OpenMM²⁶, OpenMMTools²², and the now deprecated Yank²⁷.

Figure 21: Example absolute binding free energy thermodynamic cycle. Here charges are fully annihilated while the VdW interactions are decoupled.

Protocols for both hydration and binding free energies are being added with the latter implemented using automatically picked Boresch-style restraints. Validation of the hydration free energy protocol demonstrates good agreement with experimental data and previously calculated values (Figure 22). Binding free energies are still in the process of being validated, having been hindered by the Ambertools partial charge bugs reported below.

Figure 22: Validation of the hydration free energy Protocol, a) comparison of calculated estimates against experiment, and b) comparison of estimates with previously calculated values for the 2.0 release of the Sage OpenFF force field⁵.

Supporting Tooling

As well as producing free energy methods, the team has also been working on tooling for the preparation and analysis of these methods.

Lomap

Following feedback from consortium members, the performance of the Lomap atom mapping tool was evaluated. The performance of Lomap is particularly critical in advanced/optimal network creation where all N^2 atom mappings in a N ligand dataset must be created, leading to poor scaling. We identified a cheminformatics trick whereby, to find the maximum common substructure (MCS) between pairs of many related compounds, first we find the MCS between all compounds, and use this as a seed for the multiple pairwise searches. This strategy has improved performance of the Lomap tool between 10 and 60 times.

The code of Lomap has been refactored to allow the direct usage of the various independent algorithms (atom mapping, mapping scoring, and network creation) within the overall package. As well as being a valuable asset for the programmatic use of this tool by developers, this is an important step in future possibilities for new algorithms.

Kartograf

Kartograf contains an atom mapper that allows very fast mapping of ligands' atoms onto each other based on their coordinates. Based on feedback that reached us, considering occasionally occurring challenges with stereochemistry, molecule symmetries, and the speed of Lomap, we designed the atom mapping algorithm of Kartograf. One benefit of Kartograf is that the coordinates are mostly preserved in the atom mappings, intrinsically preserving the binding mode and stereochemistry of a system due to its 3D geometry-based approach. In contrast to Lomap, this algorithm does not use MCS and therefore is significantly faster than Lomap, but it depends heavily on the input coordinates given by the user. In our current benchmarking efforts with RBEF calculations, we showed that Kartograf can produce good atom mappings, yielding comparable results to Lomap. This work was published in *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 2024, 20, 5, 1862–1877. More information about Kartograf can be found in the publication ([Kartograf: An Accurate Geometry-Based Atom Mapper for Hybrid Topology Relative Free Energy Calculations](#)) and the [Kartograf documentation](#).

Figure 23: Algorithmic approach of Kartograf's atom mapper

Foreign Input Ingestion

Interoperability with existing workflows and practices is a key aim both to allow easy adoption of our software but also to facilitate easy comparison between different methods. One example of this is functions that were added to ingest FEP networks from either Orion (`openfe.ligand_network_planning.load_fepplus_network`) or FEP+ (`openfe.ligand_network_planning.load_fepplus_network`). In the near future, capability to load Maestro (.mae) files will be added, so that pre-prepared inputs can be imported to open source workflows. This is currently undergoing validation to check that inputs are not becoming mangled.

Cinnabar

Correct plotting and analysis of results is important both for interpretation as well as communication. Cinnabar, originally called arsenic but renamed to avoid a clash with an existing software package, was designed to meet this goal of faithfully plotting results and avoiding any intentional or unintentional errors which can bias statistics. This tool had fallen out of maintenance as the original developers had progressed onto new ventures, and so was adopted by the Open Free Energy team.

Figure 23: Example plot generated by cinnabar

The cinnabar tool solves the problem of handling the results of multiple calculations in a **network** of values. This tool allowed many important features such as performing maximum-likelihood-estimation of absolute free energies and plotting results according to agreed community best practices. One deficit however is that it was focussed purely on retrospective benchmarking applications, making its use for prospective usage limited. Work this year has allowed cinnabar to plot prospective benchmarking results, as well as building a programming API to allow advanced usage of the package. As we move forwards to look at scaffold hopping and combinations of relative and absolute calculations, cinnabar will remain at the core of network level analysis of results.

Key Collaborations

The OpenFE team has engaged in several mutually beneficial collaborations this year. These not only have enabled an increase in uptake of the OpenFE frameworks, but have also allowed us to stay ahead of the curve in enabling upcoming technologies and promoting best practices. Here we list some of the key projects and direct collaborations which OpenFE has been involved in.

Open Force Field

The Open Force Field Consortium continues to be a key partner of the Open Free Energy project. As key users of their force fields and toolkit components, OpenFE is engaged to participate in testing and adopting the latest developments from OpenFF. Key points of collaboration included short benchmarking evaluations of the 2.1 release of the OpenFF SMIRNOFF force field (Figure 24) and the NAGL model for partial charge assignment. Next year, we hope to participate in testing new features such as off site charges and the Rosemary protein force field.

Figure 24: Comparison of OpenFF 2.0 and 2.1 calculated $\Delta\Delta G$ values for five benchmark systems.Figure 25: Evaluation of calculated $\Delta\Delta G$ values using NAGL machine-learned partial charges (calculated) against OpenEye OECHMELF10 partial charges (reference) for four benchmark systems.

Perses

With the OpenFE RFE Protocol being based on Perses, the OpenFE team has been working closely with the Perses team (particularly John Chodera, Ivan Pulido and Ivy Zhang) in continuing to adopt and migrate their advancements into OpenFE-enabled tooling.

Of particular note, this year has seen work by Ivan in implementing a Non-Equilibrium Cycling Protocol which can be found in <https://github.com/choderalab/fefflow/tree/main/fefflow>. Work is still in progress to evaluate this Protocol against the equilibrium RFE Protocol currently available in OpenFE, however early results seem to indicate good reproducibility of results (Figure X). Other ongoing work are currently underway to consolidate by migrating code upstream to places such as OpenMMTools.

Figure 26: Comparison of calculated $\Delta\Delta G$ values for the TYK2 benchmark system using both Non-Equilibrium Cycling (NeCycling) and the OpenFE RFE Protocol with Hamiltonian Replica Exchange (HREX).

Alchemiscale

OpenFE has continued to participate in the development of [Alchemiscale](#), a joint collaboration between OpenFF and the ASAP consortium to enable the use of distributed computing services (e.g. Folding@Home) for running free energy calculations. Access to Alchemiscale deployments have allowed OpenFE to carry out large scale benchmarks which would otherwise not be feasible with limited compute resources.

Protein-Ligand Benchmarks

Members of the OpenFE team have continued to participate in remedial efforts led by the Chodera lab (John Chodera, Melissa Boby, Ivan Pudilo, and Jenke Scheen) to address limitations with the existing^{28,29}. Efforts have continued to focus on the development of a new set of standardized inputs which improve adherence to best practices. Current work is focusing on calculating new free energy estimates for the newly prepared inputs and identifying any areas of regression in the dataset compared to previous releases.

Mobley lab

The OpenFE team has been collaborating with members of David Mobley's lab with the aim of co-evaluating tooling. This year this has taken the form of;

- Assessing and improving network generation tooling, including both HiMap and LoMap (Mary Pitman)
- Co-evaluating the OpenFE tooling on new benchmark sets (Meghan Osato). This work has been key to identifying the partial charge bugs reported under Ecosystem Maintenance.

The Future of Open Free Energy

The future of OpenFE is being written by the decisions of the Advisory Board, the guidance of the TAC, and the efforts of the project team. The current state of the project as reported here provides a functional foundation for exciting new developments to come.

Short Term Objectives

In 2024, OpenFE is engaged in a large-scale benchmarking effort in collaboration with nearly all of our industry partners. In Phase 1, our partners are performing free energy calculations using openfe v1.0 on a wide range of target sets previously published by Schrodinger as a [benchmark of their FEP+ software](#). In Phase 2, they will use the same approach to perform free energy calculations on their own internal target sets. We will continue to work closely with our partners through the second half of 2024, with the aim of publishing these results (without publishing the targets or chemistry of the Phase 2 systems).

In addition to assessing the accuracy of our software, we are continuing to develop new features and methods. We are currently working on a new toolset for manipulating alchemical networks to enable more sophisticated simulation campaigns. We are also implementing support for Gromacs as an alternative MD engine in place of OpenMM, finishing work on an Absolute Binding Free Energy (ABFE) protocol, and beginning work on an implementation of the Separated Topologies method. We are also exploring options for delivering a new execution engine to facilitate running large simulation campaigns in an HPC environment, for supporting the anticipated release of an OpenFF force field with virtual sites (off-site charges), and for supporting custom force field parameters from the BespokeFit tool.

Long Term Vision

The central goal of OpenFE is to provide functionality competitive with commercially available software. While the project aims to meet the scientific needs (methodological and performance related) of partners, provisioning a graphical user interface (GUI) is out of scope for the project. Instead, we intend to partner with software vendors to provide this.

Finally, a guiding strategy of the project is to try and engage other members of the open source software community. Working collaboratively with new and existing efforts in the field can only help the project in maximizing its output, enabling the team to deliver more than the sum of its parts. To this end, the project has

engaged with various academic collaborators and written letters in support of grant applications. This has included letters of support in grant applications for Professors Beckstein, Markland, Minh, Mobley, and Shirts. If our software proves stable and easy enough to develop that the leading academic research groups begin to implement their new methods within our ecosystem, the value of the community will far exceed the value of the methods and tools delivered by the OpenFE team. Then OpenFE will truly be a successful framework for collaboration between academia and industry.

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